

A Slant-Polarized Coaxial Slot Array Antenna Based on Gap Waveguide MLW Technology for E-Band Applications

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Abstract—This paper presents the design of a coaxial slot array antenna based on gap waveguide multilayer waveguide (MLW) technology for E-Band applications. The proposed array consists of two subarrays in a 2×4 configuration, with each element designed to generate 45° slant polarization. The design features a five-layer structure, which enables slant polarization by progressively rotating the electric field orientation by 45° through intermediate cavities. The antenna achieves an impedance bandwidth of $S_{11} < -10$ dB from 75.8 – 81.8 GHz. With 8 radiating slots, the maximum achieved gain is 14.7 dBi.

Index Terms—Joint communications and sensing, radar applications, multilayer waveguide, slant polarization.

I. INTRODUCTION

Joint communication and sensing (JCAS) systems are becoming increasingly important in emerging applications, particularly autonomous smart vehicles [1]. These systems offer significant benefits by sharing hardware and spectrum and enabling mutual information exchange [2]. Future autonomous vehicles will be equipped with advanced sensors that will allow higher levels of autonomous driving. By sharing sensor data among vehicles, these systems can extend the sensing range, leading to improved safety features [3]. However, challenges remain, particularly in achieving effective isolation between communication and sensing signal paths or transmitter (TX) and receiver (RX) signal paths. Interference between beamforming fields of antennas is another key issue. Various system-level techniques have been developed to improve this isolation, whether between the communication and sensing or between TX and RX components. From a hardware perspective, polarization diversity is a well-known approach to improve isolation between antennas. Indeed, using orthogonally polarized antennas reduces self-interference (SI) between beamforming antenna patterns and reduces the mutual coupling between antenna components [4], [5]. For example, a dual-polarized multi-beam antenna based on a 3D-printed ridged waveguide was proposed for radar and communication systems in [6]. However, the antenna structure suffers from limited impedance bandwidth.

Millimeter-wave (mmWave) antennas are ideal candidates for integrating communication and sensing functions due to

Fig. 1. Dispersion diagram for the infinite periodic EBG unit cell.

their large bandwidths and compact size. Individual functions within a unified system also benefit from mmWave antennas because they help to increase data rate for communication, and enrich target information for sensing, in addition to improving isolation between radar channels in an automotive radar system.

Gap waveguide antennas offer a high-gain solution to conventional hollow waveguides by confining electromagnetic wave propagation within their guiding structure. At mmWaves, gap waveguides show low dielectric and transmission losses. In JCAS systems, multiple linearly polarized gap waveguide antennas can be adjacently positioned by jointly designing the antenna system to improve the isolation between components, as shown in studies such as [7], [8], and [9].

Another promising method to realize efficient mmWave antennas is the multilayer waveguide (MLW) technique, recently proposed in [10]. This method provides an alternative to air-filled waveguides, enabling reduced array element separation without using dielectric materials. The MLW supports the transverse electromagnetic (TEM) propagation mode in

TABLE I
DIMENSIONS OF MLW COAXIAL SLOT ANTENNA.

Parameter	W	L	Ch _w	S _w	Corr _w
Value (mm)	12	17.5	1.5	0.85	0.8
Parameter	D	Pin _w	Pin _l	Slotc _w	Slotc _l
Value (mm)	2.2	0.7	0.7	0.47	2.17
Parameter	Slotc _t	Cav _w	Cav _l	Cav _t	Cav _d
Value (mm)	1.45	2.1	3.5	1.23	0.51
Parameter	Slotr _w	Slotr _l			
Value (mm)	0.45	2.27			

stacked multiple unconnected thin metal layers. In [11], a slotted array antenna with horizontal polarization for automotive radar applications was designed using a low-loss air-filled coaxial waveguide transmission line based on MLW technology.

In this paper, we propose a solution for 45° slant polarization using an MLW antenna, exploiting polarization diversity for the benefit of JCAS and radar systems. The 45° and the -45° slant polarizations can be used in such unified/hybrid systems. The following sections will outline the antenna's design process and present optimized results.

II. MLW COAXIAL LINE DESIGN

An initial version of this approach was introduced in [12], aiming to reduce the spacing between array elements without requiring dielectric materials in coaxial lines that support a TEM mode. In this design, small stubs positioned along the coaxial line provided mechanical support for the inner conductor. However, the method proved costly and unsuitable for large-scale manufacturing. To address these issues, a more efficient technique was proposed in [11], called the multilayer waveguide (MLW). This method uses a stack of multiple unconnected thin metal layers and relies on a chemical metal etching process for manufacturing.

A. EBG Unit Cell

The Electromagnetic Bandgap (EBG) unit cell was designed to operate at the E-band, specifically targeting the desired frequency band from 76 – 81 GHz. The structure of the EBG unit cell is shown in Fig. 1 where the dimensions of the pin are depicted. It is straightforward to see that the height of the pin has been maintained as short as possible, showing the MLW technology's promising features in manufacturing and costs. The dispersion diagram shown in Fig. 1 was calculated by using CST Eigenmode solver and indicates propagation modes are not allowed from 43 – 186 GHz, achieved with a 10 μm air gap in the structure. The y and x axes denote the frequency range and wave number, respectively. This characteristic further highlights the effectiveness of the design in controlling electromagnetic wave propagation.

B. MLW Coaxial Line

This section describes the design process of the slant-polarized MLW coaxial slot array antenna.

Fig. 2. Exploded view of the proposed MLW coaxial slot array antenna.

Fig. 3. Detailed configuration of the proposed coaxial line.

As shown in Fig. 2, the MLW coaxial line is illustrated, while Fig. 3 provides a detailed view of its configuration. The antenna key dimensions are summarized in Table I. The antenna consists of five layers:

- The bottom layer features periodic Electromagnetic Bandgap (EBG) unit cells on a thin metallic substrate. A PIN-shaped EBG structure is placed along the coaxial lines to suppress any unwanted leakage of the electric fields and due to the presence of pins, no mode can propagate through them in the operating frequency band of the antenna.
- The second layer contains the coaxial line, where the inner conductor is sandwiched between the adjacent bottom and top layers. This layer feeds the coupling slots in TEM mode.
- The third layer, known as the coupling layer, includes periodic EBG unit cells and a thin substrate with coupling slots.
- The fourth layer houses cavities that gradually rotate the electric field orientation by 45°.
- The top layer, or radiation layer, contains slant slots for radiation.

Fig. 4. Electric field distribution, (a) on the coupling slot, (b) the cavity, and (c) the radiating slot.

The channel width is optimized to ensure only the desired TEM mode propagates within the antenna's operating frequency range. A power divider is used to distribute the signal evenly to two subarrays. To ensure mechanical stability, support stubs are included to connect the inner conductor to the main body of the coaxial line layer. The distance between these stubs is optimized to minimize reflection at the input port. Additionally, corrugations are added to both sides of the structure to reduce ground plane effects and suppress leakage waves, which also helps improve the antenna's gain.

Each subarray is fed by the coaxial line via two S-shaped slots with λ_g spacing between them. The distance between the slots is set to one wavelength to achieve in-phase excitation by the TEM mode, and the slots are identical to maintain symmetry in the antenna structure. However, due to λ_g spacing, grating lobes may arise, and the polarization remains horizontal at this stage.

Additional cavities are incorporated between layers to address the grating lobes and rotate the polarization. These cavities are hexagonal to optimize impedance matching at the antenna input and to equally distribute power between the two slant radiating slots. The slant slots are positioned with $\lambda_g/2$ spacing to further refine the antenna's polarization and performance.

III. SIMULATION RESULTS

The slot layouts in different layers, along with the simulated electric field distribution in the slots are shown in Fig. 4. The first slotted layer, featuring the S-shape slots, generates horizontal electric field components shown in Fig. 4(a), while the subsequent cavity layer rotates these components by 45° each shown in Fig. 4(b). As shown in Fig. 4(c), the electric fields are effectively coupled to the slant slots. Due to the in-phase excitation of the slots and the $\lambda_g/2$ spacing between them, the antenna achieves a uniform radiation pattern.

Fig. 5 presents the reflection coefficient of the antenna and the realized gain at broadside direction across various frequencies. The antenna has good performance in the frequency band from 75.8 – 81.8 GHz offering the required impedance bandwidth at $S_{11} < -10$ dB for automotive 77 GHz radars.

Fig. 5. Simulated input reflection coefficient and gain of the proposed antenna.

Fig. 6. Co-polarized and X-polarized simulated patterns of the antenna at frequencies 77, 78, and 79 GHz (a) E-plane and (b) H-plane.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. (a) Front to Back ratio and Side Lobe Level of the antenna versus frequency and (b) Cross Polarization ratio.

The simulated E- and H-plane radiation patterns at 77, 78, and 79 GHz are shown in Fig. 6. In Fig. 7, additional details about the quality of the radiation patterns are presented. The front-to-back ratio, depicted in Fig. 7(a), is approximately 30 dB, indicating the strong directivity of the antenna in the broadside direction. The SLL values in the same figure demonstrate the low magnitude of grating lobes in the E- and H-plane. It is worth mentioning that to additionally improve the side lobe level with a higher number of slots in the antenna, slot tapering might be handy. Fig. 7(b) illustrates the cross-polarization ratio of the radiation patterns, where the minimum cross-polarization ratio is observed near the broadside direction. The proposed antenna exhibits a favorable cross-polarization ratio and features a much thinner structure compared to the Gap waveguide antennas described in [4] and [9]. By adding two additional layers to the conventional three-layer horizontally polarized MLW antenna, the proposed design achieves slant polarization while maintaining a compact form factor. Notably, the antenna remains significantly com-

pact relative to other technologies, with an overall height of just 0.9 mm, i.e., 5.3 times thinner than the Gap waveguide antenna in [9], which has a height of 4.8 mm. As mentioned above, chemical metal etching is used as a manufacturing method for MLW antennas. However, due to the thin layers and small slots in the antenna structure, there will always be some dimensional tolerances in the prototyped models compared to the simulated designs. These discrepancies can slightly impact the antenna's performance. To mitigate this issue, it is important to account for these tolerances during the simulation process.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The simulation results confirm that the proposed slant-polarized coaxial slot array antenna is a highly suitable solution for E-band applications, such as joint communication and sensing (JCAS) systems and automotive radar. One key advantage of this design is its ability to significantly reduce self-interference, especially when used in conjunction with an orthogonally polarized antenna, e.g. a similar array with a rotated polarization by 90° . This enhanced isolation is critical in JCAS systems, where communication and sensing functions operate simultaneously, and in radar applications, where minimizing interference is essential for accurate detection and performance.

The antenna's wide impedance bandwidth within the 75.8 to 81.8 GHz range ensures reliable operation over a broad spectrum, providing flexibility for high-data-rate communication and precise sensing in automotive and industrial scenarios. Moreover, the high-gain fixed beam at the broadside makes it ideal for applications requiring focused, stable signal transmission or reception. This feature is particularly useful for radar systems and point-to-point communication links, where maintaining strong signal integrity and directionality is important.

For both practitioners and researchers, this antenna design offers a robust, cost-effective solution that leverages multilayer waveguide (MLW) technology, providing key performance benefits like polarization diversity, wide bandwidth, and high gain, while addressing the challenges of self-interference and signal integrity in advanced E-band systems.

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